

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI
OLIY TA'LIM, FAN VA INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
MIRZO ULUG'BEK NOMIDAGI
O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETI

“O‘ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETINING ILM- FAN RIVOJI VA JAMIYAT TARAQQIYOTIDA TUTGAN O‘RNI”

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy
konferensiyasi materiallari

TO‘PLAMI - II

 2023 yil 12-may

Toshkent-2023

**O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI
OLIV TA'LIM, FAN VA INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
MIRZO ULUG'BEK NOMIDAGI O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETI**

**O'ZBEKISTON MILLIY UNIVERSITETINING ILM-FAN RIVOJI VA JAMIYAT
TARAQQIYOTIDA TUTGAN O'RNI**

mavzusidagi Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi materiallari to'plami
(II-qism)
(2023-yil 12-may)

Toshkent - 2023

“O‘zbekiston Milliy universitetining ilm-fan rivoji va jamiyat taraqqiyotida tutgan o‘rni” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi ma’ruzalari to‘plami. Mas’ul muharrir: Y.Ergashov. – Toshkent: O‘zbekiston Milliy Universiteti, 2023-yil, 541 bet.

“O‘zbekiston Milliy universitetining ilm-fan rivoji va jamiyat taraqqiyotida tutgan o‘rni” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi ma’ruzalari to‘plamida universitet, respublika oliy ta’lim muassalari hamda ilmiy va ishlab chiqarish tashkilotlarida ilmiy faoliyat olib borayotgan olimlar, professor-o‘qituvchilar, yosh olimlar hamda tadqiqotchilarning ilmiy tadqiqot natijalari mujassamlashgan.

Mas’ul muharrir – Y.Ergashov, f.-m.f.d., professor

Tahrir hay’ati – O.Zikirov, f.-m.f.d., professor

Z.Raxmonov, f.-m.f.d., dotsent

G’Eshonqulov, f.-m.f.n., dotsent

Sh.Kadirova, k.f.d., professor

T.Abduraxmonov, b.f.n., professor

Sh.Sharipov, g.f.d., dotsent

A.Umarov, g.-m.f.n., dotsent

A.Mo‘minov, s.f.d., professor

K.Inakov, p.f.n., dotsent

M.Mirsoatova, f.f.n., dotsent

A.Umarov, i.f.n., dotsent

K.Raxmonov, g.f.n., dotsent

V.Raximov, p.f.n., professor

R.Allaberdiyev, b.f.n., dotsent

H.Boltaboyev, f.f.d., professor

X.Bakiyev

Nashrga tayyorlovchilar – N.Aliyev; Sh.Adashboyev, Z.Pardayev, N.Nurmuamedova

Mazkur to‘plamga kiritilgan maqola va tezislarning mazmun mohiyati, ilmiy asoslanganligi, undagi me’yoriy-huquqiy hujjatlarning to‘g‘riligi hamda tanqidiy fikr-mulohazalar va keltirilgan takliflarga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldir.

MODERN SOLUTIONS OF CLASSIC GENRES

Kazakbaeva D.

National University of Uzbekistan

Abstract: It is a fact that the need to research literary forms and genres is several times greater than in other types of literary studies. Therefore, the research of literary types and genres is one of the problems that require a lot of research not only in Uzbek literature, but also in world literary studies.

Keywords: World and Uzbek classical literature studies, literary types and genres, poetics, classical genres, principles of modern development.

Introduction

The research of literary types and genres in literary studies is considered as one of the priority scientific problems at the level of Uzbek and world literary studies. In particular, much work remains to be done in defining the precise boundaries of literary types, forms of expression and genres in world and Uzbek classical literature, studying the possibilities of poetic content expressed through these genres, and researching the artistry of genres.

Even now, the study of the literary genre and its features falls within the competence of poetics. Therefore, one of the tasks facing world literary studies is the gradual disclosure of the nature of individual genres by studying specific aspects of the literary text genre in connection with other issues of poetics.

Each poetic genre has its own fixed structure, and the study of the artistry of a certain work, along with the study of its genre features, is one of the accepted scientific methods in world literature. Although the classical genres differ in structure, their character is mainly determined by the meter, rhyming strophic characteristics of the works created in this genre. The study of such aspects typical of classical poetry genres is directly the main task of the literary studies science.

The increasing attention to the study of classical works in the world of literary studies poses actual and important challenges to the literary science of the new era. In particular, the study of the issues of the literary type and genre, their scientific and theoretical research is still one of the topical problems of literary studies. The study of the nature of classical genres and works written in these genres has not lost its relevance, and now, especially more seriously studied the nature of ghazal, rubai and other subgenres. However, among genres of classical poetry, *the genres with a complex structure* are relatively less studied, and it determines the relevance of the study, based on the current scientific necessity and literary needs in Uzbek literary studies.

Methods

In this sense, the study of literary types and genres in literary studies and public research serves the intellectual growth of people, it is one of the important links in the education in the spirit of national and universal values.

The development of culture, art, science and literature in the period of Eastern classical literature, as well as researches related to the study of the structure of poetry are conducted in a number of leading scientific centers of the world, including Oxford University, Cambridge University (Great Britain); دانشگاه مشهد فردوسی, تهران دانشگاه (Iran); İstanbul Üniversitesi, Ankara Üniversitesi, Gazi Üniversitesi (Turkey); Balkh State University (Afghanistan), Aligarh Muslim University, Delhi University (India); Azərbaycan milli elmlər akademiyası Nizami adına ədəbiyyat İnstitutu və Z.Bünyadov adına Şərqişnaslıq İnstitutu (Azerbaijan); Vostochnyy fakultet pri SPbGU, Institut vostochnykh rukopisey v Sankt-Peterburge (Russia); Institute vostokovedeniya A. Krymskogo; Донишгоҳи миллии Тоҷикистон (Tajikistan); Institute of Uzbek Language, Literature and Folklore, National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies, Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature, Samarkand State University, International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan (Uzbekistan).

In world poetry the researches are being carried out in the following directions in order to study poetic systems using new approaches and technical possibilities: theoretical and practical comparison of ancient and modern meters and their internal structure, poetry type of meter, rhyme, rhythm, stress, study of the proportions of elements; identifying the specifics of new approaches, views and theories in poetry; compiling manuscripts related to the theory of complex structural genres; development of modern computer-based programs and research methods of complex structural genres.

Results and Discussion

Research on the science of classical poetry was carried out in different periods on the basis of different means and methods. The strophe system, the principles of its development, the problems of the development of poetry attracted the attention of researchers in all historical periods. In the world and Uzbek literary studies, the science of aruz and artistry, which forms a single unit with the science of poetry, has been sufficiently researched. However, the study of treatises on the theory of complex structural genres, the lack of completed research on this science, and the fact that the stage of formation of Turkic poetry is not studied, makes it necessary to study this science in the historical-comparative aspect. The scientists F. Gladwin [1,11-12], Daudpota U. (India) [2,34], A. Arberry (London) [3,19-20] H. Bloshman [4,8], B. Reinert (Germany) [5,33-34], D. De Wees [6,5-8], M. Simidcheva (Canada) [7,51-55], E.G. Browne [8,13-15], Clinton J.W. (USA) [9,8], H.Boltaboev [10,56-67], D.Kazakbaeva (Uzbekistan) [11,8-21], in their research put the problems related to the literary sciences that developed widely in the Middle Ages, in particular, the special features of Arabic, Persian, and Turkic poetry, classical poetics, as examples of treatises dedicated to ilmi aruz, ilmi qafiya, ilmi badi', ilmi baloga, and expressed their views on them.

In world literary studies the scholars such as J.S. Meisami (Great Britain), V.M. Zhirmunsky, M.L. Reiser, B. Ya. Shidfar, I. M. Filshinsky, M-N. Osmanov, D. Samoilov, M. L. Gasparov (Russia), J. Landau (France), B. Sirius, Kh. Sharifov, R. H. Hadizoda, A. Sattarzoda, T. Mardon, S. J. Chillaev (Tajikistan), H. Usmonov, M. Bakirov (Tataristan), M. K. Khamraev, Z. A. Akhmetov, A. Tilavaldi (Kazakhstan), K. Risaliev (Kyrgyzstan), A. Bekmuradov (Turkmenistan) have researched the history

and principles of modern development of Arabic, Persian, Tajik, Azerbaijani, Tatar, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Turkmen, and Uzbek poetics, including the system of images, artistic tools, and the strophe basis of classical literature.

However, the fact that the development of poetics, which has an important place in determining the historical progress and development of science of poetry, strophe studies has not been fundamentally studied as a scientific problem, the problems of science of poetry in the treatises of the classical literature period have not been historically and theoretically researched at the level of the units of poetry, shows that this scientific work is different from the previous ones. And the aim of this research is to carry out a comparative analysis of the poetry of Uzbek classical literature period in terms of theoretical, practical, poetic elements, scientific substantiation of tendencies of historical development and its specific features. The theoretical sources of the complex structural genres created in Uzbek classical poetry, the development of these genres until the beginning of the 20th century, their transformation in terms of form and content, and their historical improvement are analyzed based on the requirements of modern literary studies. Based on the aim of the research, scientific research includes the following sequence of priority tasks:

Table 1

is examined in

1	- introduction of sources related to complex structural genres into scientific circulation;
2	- determining the specific characteristics of each genre by studying the theoretical foundations of genres with a complex structure;
3	- classification of complex structural genres in classical poetry and determination of their historical development factors;
4	- determining the development of genres with a complex structure in the period before Navoi;
5	- to give conclusions about the relationship of complex structural genres to other genres as a result of scientifically based analysis;
6	- to study the historical development of genres with complex structure in Navoi works and during his time, theoretical views about genres;
7	- determining the expression of musammat forms and large-scale genres in Navoi's work;
8	- classification of complex structural genres in the literature of the 16th-19th centuries;
9	- to show the development, improvement and consistency of complex structural genres in the literary environment of Bukhara, Kokand and Khiva and draw scientifically based conclusions

The subject of the research is the analysis of historical factors and theoretical foundations of the formation and development of complex structural genres, their differences from other classical poetic genres, as well as the poetic characteristic of works written in this genre. The principles of historicity, rationality, theory, complementarity have been observed when conducting research with a systemic approach to the problem. Descriptive, comparative-historical, systematization and statistical methods were used in the research process.

Despite the fact that the issue of literary types and genres has been consistently studied in literary studies, the issue of complex structural genres in classical literature is being studied in science for the first time in a monographic plan. It is precisely this aspect of the issue that determines the scientific novelty of the research.

1. In the research of the problem of literary types and genres in Uzbek classical literature, taking into account that complex structural genres have not been historically and theoretically studied in a monographic plan, the study of the works taken as the object of research on the basis of the requirements of classical literature and today's literary studies determines the scientific novelty of the research.

2. In the research, genres with complex structure are observed in the example of artistic and scientific analysis of samples of Uzbek classical literature.

3. Common and unique issues of the genres of classical works in the literature of Uzbek and Eastern peoples are studied.

4. In the process of analysis of complex structural genres, their genre features, mystical, Sufi, philosophical and rindona (*freethinking*) topics are highlighted.

5. The issue of complex structural genres:

- ilmi aruz (*science on aruz*);
- ilmi qafiya (*science on rhyme*);
- ilmi badi' (*poetics*) are revealed.

6. The idea of the author, the system of traditional images, the role of the plot and composition in the structure of the work in the development of classical literature, and the continuation of classical traditions in the works are analyzed;

7. The importance of complex structural genres in the history of Uzbek literature is proven on the basis of historical analysis;

8. It is proved that Alisher Navoi's work is superior in terms of ideological and artistic features, rhyme, poetic size and poetic figures, it is within the scope of topics such as Sufi, religious-educational, metaphorical love and real love;

9. In the work of the poets of the generation after Alisher Navoi, the traditionalism in the interpretation of images in complex structural genres, the fact that they were effectively influenced by the works of their predecessors, and the proportionality of form and content in the internal structure of their works and their uniqueness in harmony with the idea of the work are revealed.

Figure.1.text

The practical results of the research are expected to be:
definition and systematization of theoretical bases of works in genres created during the period of Uzbek classical literature;
research of factors of Uzbek and Persian-Tajik poetry development from a comparative-historical point of view;
during the period of Uzbek classical literature, Uzbek and Persian-Tajik poetry have common roots, it has been proved that it exists as a single unit and is the product of the same cultural and literary environment;
definition of theoretical treatises role in the development of the Eastern classical poetics.

Conclusion

The study of fundamental scientific and theoretical views of scientists of our country and foreign countries on the history and modern development of the science of literary types and genres, primary literary written monuments, in particular, manuscript copies of "Funun ul-Balagha" stored in the Bodleian Library in Great Britain, Elliott No.127 inventory, were included and used in the scope of the research. The conclusions of the study and the recommendations are based on their implementation. It defines the adequacy of the study aim and tasks, the implementation of conclusions, proposals and recommendations, and the approval of the results by official organizations.

The scientific and practical significance of the research lies in the improvement of research works in the field of Uzbek and Eastern classical poetics, in particular views on the theory of literary types and genres, theoretical conclusions and recommendations on sources, for further acceleration of the direction of poetry and aruz studies, the topic is defined by the fact that it can be used as a scientific and theoretical source in researching the issues of literary relations and literary influence, creating research and monographs.

Practical significance of the research results lies in creation of innovative textbooks and teaching aids on the basis of the conclusions and recommendations of dissertations on disciplines "History of Uzbek Literature", "Basics of Aruz and Classical Poetics", "Navoi studies", improvement of the content of lectures and seminars, development of optional classes and special courses "Uzbek Language" is explained by the fact that it that it can be used to improve the content of subjects such as "World Literature" with theoretical conclusions.

References

1. Gladwin F. "Dissertations on the Rhetoric, Prosody and Rhyme of the Persians", -Calcutta, 1801.
2. Daudpota U. "The Influence of Arabic Poetry on the Development of Persian Poetry". -Bombay, 1934.
3. Arberry A. "Classical Persian Literature", -London, 1958.
4. Blochmann H. Prosody of the Persians according to Saifi, Jami and other writers. -Calcutta, 1872.
5. Reinert B. "Probleme der vormongolischen arabisch-persischen Poesiegemeinschaft und ihr Reflex in der Poetik", // "Arabic Poetry: Theory and Development", -Wiesbaden, 1973.
6. DeWeese D. The Predecessors of Nava'i in the "Funun al-balagah" of Shaykh Ahmad b. Khudaydad Tarazi: a neglected source on Central Asian literary culture from the fifteenth century // Turkish studies, edited by Sinasi Tekin, 2005, volume 29.
7. Simidchieva M. Imitation and Innovation in Timurid Poetics: Kashifi's Badayi al-afkar and Predecessors, al-Mu'jam and Hada'iq al-sihr // Iraninan Studies, volume 36, number 4, 2003.
8. Browne E.G. "A Literary History of Persia from the Earliest Times to Modern Times", Vol. 2, Cambridge, 1964.
9. Clinton J.W. "Shams-i Qays on the Nature of Poetry", "Edebiyat", n.s. 1, № 2, c. 101 – 128, Philadelphia, 1985.
10. Classical poetics of the East. In the interpretation of Hamidulla Boltaboev. - T.: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, 2008.
11. D. Kazakbaeva. Development of tarjiband and tarkibband genres in Uzbek classical literature. Thesis of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) on Philol. sciences. - T., 2022.

61. OBJECTIVE AND SUBJECTIVE FACTORS DETERMINING THE BEHAVIOR OF YOUNG VOTERS IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN	184
Jiyanmuratova G.....	184
62. LINGUA-COACHING AS A NEW APPROACH TO TEACHING ESP	186
Jurayeva G.B.	186
63. THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN MONOCHRONIC AND POLYCHRONIC TIME	189
Jurayeva M.	189
64. ULUGBEK KHAMDAM'S WRITING STRATEGY	191
Kamilova S, Arustamyan Y.....	191
65. ON THE WAY TO THE DIGITAL EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN	192
Kamolov D.	192
66. O'ZBEKISTON RAQAMLI TA'LIM TIZIMI YO'LIDA	194
Kamolov D.R.	194
67. SOCIAL AND POLITICAL ACTIVITY OF REPRESENTATIVES OF THE MIDDLE AGE MYSTICISMS	196
Kandakharov A.Kh.....	196
68. O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASINING FAXRIY UNVONLARI	200
Karimjonov J.....	200
69. PEDAGOGICAL BASES OF TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS	203
Karimova M. O.....	203
70. THE ROLE OF LAPIS LAZULI IN CENTRAL ASIA IN THE PERIOD OF THE BRONZE AGE	206
Kattaeva G., Khamidov O.	206
71. MODERN SOLUTIONS OF CLASSIC GENRES	210
Kazakbaeva D.	210
72. CLASSICAL POETIC GENRES IN THE INTERPRETATION OF ABDURAUF FITRAT	213
Kazakbayeva D.J., G'ulomova H.Y.....	213
73. UNIVERSITY GOVERNANCE AND TERTIARY ENROLLMENT: STATISTICS, RELATIONSHIPS AND SOLUTIONS	214
Khasanov.A.....	214
74. EUROPE AND THE EAST IN THE STUDY OF THE FAMILY INSTITUTE VIEWS OF SCIENTISTS	217
Kholdorov M.	217
75. WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF BANKING SERVICES IN UZBEKISTAN	220
Khuzhayorov Kh.	220
76. PROSPECTS FOR THE STUDY OF THE PROBLEMS OF CHRONOLOGY AND STRATIGRAPHY OF THE EARLY ANTHROPOGEN IN THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN	224
Krakhmal K. A.	224
77. METHODS OF USING INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN DETERMINING THE SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL CONTENT OF LABORATORY WORK ON PHYSICS AND THEIR IMPLEMENTATION ..	228
Kurbanov.M, Kurbanov.Kh.....	228
78. GENRE TRADITIONS OF THE FAMILY SAGA IN THE NOVEL "LAZARUS'S WOMEN" BY MARINA STEPNOVA	231
Kurchastova A.....	231
79. THE HARMONY AND EDUCATIONAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE CONCEPT OF DESIGN WITH ETHICS, AESTHETICS	233
Madaminov N.M.....	233
80. INTRODUCING MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING SUBJECTS TO STUDENTS IN DRAWING LESSONS	236
Mamatov D.X., Soxibov R.J.	236
81. DEVELOPMENT OF DEVELOPMENT OF CERAMICS	239
Mamurov A.A.....	239